

The Dynamics of Dutch Disease in Coffee-Producing Economies

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Abstract

Coffee producing countries have large production capacities, but the inefficient use of the income earned from the export of this product may have a negative impact on the economic growth rate. The fact that coffee producing countries are the world leaders in terms of coffee production and exports increases the possibility of the Dutch Disease problem in these countries. This has been the main motivation for investigating the existence of Dutch Disease in coffee-producing countries. In this study, the effect of Dutch Disease in the agricultural sector was analyzed by using the variables of coffee production amount, real exchange rate, GDP (gross domestic product), agricultural added value, exports, foreign direct investments and foreign trade deficit of Brazil, Colombia, Indonesia, Honduras, Mexico, Guatemala, Vietnam, Uganda, India, which produce the best coffee among the coffee producing countries and rank first in terms of production amount for the period 1989-2022. The long-term relationship between the variables was examined using the Pedroni panel cointegration test, and a significant cointegration relationship was found in the panel group. Long-term coefficient estimates were obtained using the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) method. The coefficients were found to be statistically significant in both country-level and panel-level analyses. However, no direct evidence was found to support the existence of Dutch Disease. This finding was supported by the Hurlin panel causality test, which revealed that coffee production and exports did not lead to structural deterioration in the agricultural sector, indicating that no Dutch Disease effect was observed.

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1. Introduction

The Dutch Disease, a much-discussed economic phenomenon that refers to the disruption caused by rising commodity revenues in non-commodity tradable sectors, is the title of an article published in *The Economist* in 1977 about the impact of the discovery of natural gas in the North Sea on the Dutch economy. The high foreign exchange earnings from gas exports in the Netherlands caused changes in prices and exchange rates. Due to the exchange rate change in the Netherlands, exporters in sectors where they were previously competitive lost their market share, and thus both production and exports decreased in these sectors (Barder, 2006; Yépez, 2021; Middelanis, 2022). Briefly, the term Dutch Disease refers to the negative effects of natural gas discoveries in the 1960s on Dutch production, in fact through the subsequent appreciation of the Dutch real exchange rate (Corden, 1984). Although Dutch Disease is generally associated with mineral resources, it is also possible to include the increase in wealth resulting from large foreign exchange inflows (foreign aid, remittances and capital inflows) and export booms in sectors other than mining within the analytical framework of Dutch disease (Brahmbhatt et al., 2010; Kojo, 2015). During the Dutch Disease process, when the discovered natural resource is oil or mineral, stagnation in agriculture and agricultural production may occur (Brahmbhatt et al., 2010). Another name for the Dutch disease in the literature is the natural resource curse, which can be defined as the chronic overvaluation of the exchange rate due to the excessive use of a country's abundant and cheap resources (Bresser-Pereira, 2008). Stiglitz (2004) defined the concept of Dutch disease by associating it with economic performance. According to this definition, the worse performance of economies with large natural resources than economies less endowed in terms of natural resources is called the natural resource curse. In this context, it is possible to say that the Dutch Disease has become an interesting phenomenon for economists in the literature. The theoretical foundations of Dutch Disease

were explained by Corden and Neary (1982) and Corden (1984). In these studies, three sectors (the booming sector, the declining sector and the non-tradable sector) were considered. In the evolving process between these three sectors, two effects emerge: the spending effect and the resource movement effect. The resource movement effect refers to the reallocation of production factors from the declining, i.e. less competitive, sector, and from the non-tradable sector to the booming sector. The spending effect is the effect of increased income that expands domestic aggregate demand. While traded goods can be imported at international prices, non-tradable goods must be produced domestically. As a result, the spending effect increases the price of non-tradable goods relative to tradable goods (defined as real exchange rate appreciation in this literature), diverting resources away from the tradable sector, which does not show further development (Corden 1984; Kojo, 2014; Pasaribu, 2019). Rudd (1996) revealed in his study that there are two ways in which Dutch Disease begins. In the first of these ways, the discovery of a large quantity of an easy-to-exploit oil resource can lead to rapid depletion of the resource and trigger the onset of Dutch Disease. This situation is typical of many emerging oil-exporting economies such as Nigeria and Indonesia. The discovery of the oil source and the subsequent massive exports cause the currency to appreciate, which in turn lead to the contraction of the country's traditional export sector. The second is a sudden increase in the oil prices. For example, in 1973, OPEC countries restricted oil supply and caused prices to rise from 2.59 dollars per barrel to 11.65 dollars per barrel in less than 12 months, which encouraged countries to use their existing oil reserves. This is the case in Europe's oil-exporting economies such as Norway, the United Kingdom and the Netherlands, which now find it profitable to exploit the North Sea oil and natural gas reserves. Before 1973, it was relatively unprofitable for these countries to export oil. However, the large price increase prompted European oil-exporting economies such as

Norway, the United Kingdom, and the Netherlands to begin massive exports of these resources, ultimately leading to the onset of Dutch Disease symptoms. Briefly, the Dutch Disease is when a development that is beneficial for the economy produces harmful results after a while. It is defined as the decline in total output in an economy that has acquired a sudden source of wealth as a result of the withdrawal of existing production factors from other areas of production and their diversion to the new source. This term explains the overvaluation of the national currency as a result of the abundance of foreign exchange. In the literature, this phenomenon is a consequence of the fact that some countries have natural gas, others have oil or a strategic non-natural resource good. There are many empirical studies investigating Dutch Disease in the literature. Looney (1990), Sachs and Warner (1995), Égert (2005), Kutan and Wyzan (2005), Égert and Leonard (2007), Oomes and Kalcheva (2007), Lartey (2008), Lama and Medina (2010), Algieri (2011), Corden (2011), Javaid (2011), Jayaraman and Lau (2011), Oyesanmi (2011), Arı and Özcan (2012), Égert (2012), Yardımcıoğlu and Gülmez (2013), Özdemir et al. (2018), Barczikay et al. (2020), Hien et al. (2020), Marañon and Kumral (2021), Niftiyev (2021), Asiamah et al. (2022), Biedermann et al. (2023) and Huo et al. (2023), mentioned the existence of Dutch Disease in their studies; while Ogun (1998), Sackey (2001), Atkinson and Hamilton (2003), Ouattara and Strobl (2003), Anoruo and Elike (2009), Berument et al. (2010), Ghalayani (2011), Emami and Adibpour (2012) and Mercan and Göçer (2014) emphasized the absence of Dutch Disease in their studies. Most of these studies associate Dutch disease with oil. Hao et al. (2021) and Su et al. (2021) emphasize that institutions must be developed to reverse Dutch Disease. Ma et al. (2021) argue that promoting human capital and openness is a useful factor in avoiding the Dutch Disease. A tropical climate is required for the production of coffee, which is the second most important product in the world after oil in foreign trade, and there should not be significant temperature

fluctuations throughout the year (Mbwambo et al., 2022). From this perspective, it can be said that coffee production is limited to countries with specific climate conditions. This makes coffee a strategic economic product for the countries where it is produced. In other words, coffee is a particularly important component of export for coffee-producing countries. Furthermore, global coffee consumption in the United States alone reached 1,697,000 tons in 2022, while total global consumption reached around 12,236,000 tons (World Population Review, 2025). In light of these data, it is evident that coffee consumption is high worldwide. Both its high consumption and the fact that it can only be grown under certain conditions make coffee production economically important. In the literature, studies on Dutch Disease have generally focused on products such as oil and natural gas. Studies on the agricultural sector are quite rare. When evaluated in this context, the selection of coffee, which is a strategic product in the agricultural sector, in this study is likely to contribute to the literature in terms of Dutch Disease. In addition, coffee is one of the most consumed products in the world and the fact that it is not produced everywhere contributes to the original value of this study. In line with both the purpose of the study and its original value, 9 countries with high coffee production in the world were selected. These countries are Brazil, Colombia, Indonesia, India, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico, Uganda and Vietnam. The reason for selecting these countries is both the high coffee production and the completeness of the data in the 1989-2022 period.

2. Material and Methods

This study aims to test whether the Dutch Disease hypothesis is applicable to coffee-producing countries. Additionally, it seeks to create an example of the agricultural sector for the Dutch Disease hypothesis. The method of the study was determined as panel data analysis which enables to examine both the time dimension and the cross-section dimension at the same time. This allows determining the differences and similarities

between countries, and makes it easier for the established model to provide more reliable results and make generalizations. Therefore, it was thought that panel data analysis would be more appropriate and advantageous. The study was conducted using annual data of 9 countries (Brazil, Colombia, Indonesia, India, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico, Uganda, Vietnam) whose data were accessed from the countries that produced the most coffee in the world in the period 1989-2022. While constructing Model-1, the amount of coffee production was taken as the dependent variable. The economic size and development of a country directly affects the resources and technology used in the agricultural sector. GDP growth supports investments, technology and infrastructure, which can affect coffee production. The real exchange rate is one of the key determinants of coffee production. Therefore, its impact has been sought to be observed (Ojaghlou, 2019). Exchange rate levels affect the amount of coffee production by directly affecting the competitiveness of exports, production costs, foreign trade revenues and relations with global prices. Foreign direct investment is an important factor affecting the amount of coffee production. Foreign investments can increase coffee production capacity and improve efficiency in the sector by providing

contributions in the areas of capital, technology, market access, employment and sustainability (Yılmaz, 2008). Agricultural added value is an important factor that directly affects the amount of coffee production. The production of high value-added agricultural products can increase producers' incomes and ensure more investments by encouraging more efficient, high-quality and sustainable production methods (Destek et al., 2017). Trade openness is a major factor affecting coffee production volumes. Increasing foreign trade provides access to global markets, provides producers with larger and more profitable markets, increases competition, and encourages productivity improvements. Furthermore, increasing foreign trade supports foreign investment and economic growth, allowing coffee production volumes to increase. For these reasons, GDP, exports, real exchange rate, foreign direct investment, agricultural value added and trade openness were determined as independent variables. Thus, 6 different independent variables were used in the model. Foreign direct investments (containing negative values), real exchange rate and trade openness were used in their raw form since they are proportional values, while other variables were used by taking their logarithms. The panel data models constructed in this context are shown in equation-1.

$$lyields = \beta_0 + \beta_1 rer_{it} + \beta_2 fdi_{it} + \beta_3 to_{it} + \beta_4 agr_{it} + \beta_5 exp_{it} + \beta_6 lgdp_{it} + \mu_{it} \quad (1)$$

Variables and their explanations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Variables and explanations

Abbreviation	Variable	Source
yields	Coffee, green (100 g ha ⁻¹)	FAO, 2023
rer	The Real Effective Exchange Rate (annual)	Bruegel, 2023
gdp	GDP (constant 2015 US\$)	WB, 2023
exp	Exports of goods and services (current US\$)	WB, 2023
fdi	Foreign Direct Investment, Net (BoP, current US\$)	WB, 2023
agr	Agriculture, forestry, and fishing, value added (constant 2015 US\$)	WB, 2023
to	Trade Openness=[(export+import)/GDP].100 (calculated)	WB, 2023

Using the variables given in Table 1, this study tested the validity of the Dutch disease in coffee producing countries. For this purpose, panel data analysis was used. In the study, firstly, a cross-sectional dependency test was performed for the variables using the methods of Paseran (2015, 2021), Juodis and Reese

(2021), CDw with power enhancement from Fan et al. (2015), and Paseran and Xie (2021) with 4 PCs, as the cross-sectional dependency results allow us to decide which generation unit root test will be performed. The generation of the unit root test was then determined. Unit root test results were evaluated, and it was

decided that it would be appropriate to perform cointegration test. In order to decide which cointegration test to use, cross-sectional dependency test and homogeneity test were performed on a model basis. Since cointegrated relationship was determined via cointegration analysis, panel cointegration model was estimated and obtained results were interpreted. In the study, the results were interpreted considering the 95% confidence level. The Dutch disease can disrupt the relationship between a country's natural resource wealth and its other economic variables in the long term. Cointegration

analysis can identify this long-term relationship and provide a clearer picture of how natural resources affect the economic structure.

3. Results and Discussion

Since the time dimension of the panel used in the study was $T=33$ and cross-sectional dimension was $N=9$ for coffee producing countries, cross-sectional dependence test was applied. The results of cross-section dependence test are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Cross-sectional dependence test

Variables	CD	CDw	CDw+	CD*
lyields	-1.53 (0.027)***	1.18 (0.038)***	69.95 (0.000)***	3.40 (0.001)***
lgdp	33.35 (0.000)***	7.23 (0.000)***	207.35 (0.000)***	3.70 (0.000)***
lexp	33.97 (0.000)***	7.58 (0.000)***	211.39 (0.000)***	0.52 (0.062)**
lagr	34.36 (0.000)***	7.68 (0.000)***	213.85 (0.000)***	-18.16 (0.000)***
rer	2.64 (0.008)***	0.48 (0.061)*	62.11 (0.000)**	2.16 (0.031)**
to	14.00 (0.000)**	1.15 (0.025)**	108.27 (0.000)***	1.97 (0.033)**
fdi	11.08 (0.000)**	0.27 (0.087)*	71.98 (0.000)**	2.49 (0.013)**

H_0 : weak cross-sectional dependence, H_1 : strong cross-sectional dependence, References, CD: Pesaran (2015, 2021), CDw: Juodis, Reese (2021), CDw+: CDw with power enhancement from Fan et al. (2015), CD*: Pesaran, Xie (2021) with 4 PC(s), **Note:** %1 significance level: ***, %5 significance level: **, %10 significance level: *.

According to Cross-Sectional Dependence test results in Table 2, the basic hypothesis H_0 , which expresses Cross-Section Dependence, is rejected. There is a Cross-Section Dependence between the variables. The results are statistically significant at the 5% level (Yerdelen Tatoğlu, 2024). The unit root tests to be used in cases where Cross-Section Dependence is present are the second-generation unit root tests. In this study, Fisher Phillips Perron second generation unit root test was used. The critical table values are given in Table 3. The null hypothesis H_0 of the Fisher PP unit root test given in Table 3 is "All units in the panel contain unit roots" and the alternative hypothesis is "at least one unit is stationary". Since the P-values were greater than 0.05, it was concluded that the variables contained unit roots. H_0 was accepted and it was concluded that all units in the panel

contained unit roots. When the first differences were taken to make the variables stationary, since P-values were less than 0.05, the alternative hypothesis was accepted and it was concluded that all units in the panel were stationary. It was appropriate to perform cointegration analysis according to Fisher PP unit root results. Before the cointegration analysis, the Cross-sectional dependency and homogeneity of the models for country groups should be determined. For this reason, the Cross-sectional dependency for Model 1 was examined first. In the study, since $T > N$ was in the panel data set, the presence of horizontal cross-section dependence was investigated with the "Breusch and Pagan LM Test". Table 4 shows the LM Test results for cross-section dependence for the models.

Table 3. Fisher unit root test results

Level			First difference		
lyields	Statistics	P-value	Δ lyields	Statistics	P-value
P	0.2221	0.2221	P	242.5751	0.0000***
Z	-0.4844	0.3141	Z	-13.8695	0.0000***
L*	-0.4653	0.3219	L*	-22.5256	0.0000***
Pm	0.7045	0.2406	Pm	37.4292	0.0000***
lgdp			Δ lgdp		
P	31.5272	0.250	P	116.4928	0.0000***
Z	-1.2376	0.1079	Z	-8.5811	0.0000***
L*	-1.5439	0.0645	L*	-10.7957	0.0000***
Pm	2.2545	0.0121	Pm	16.4155	0.0000***
lexp			Δ lexp		
P	13.5280	0.7593	P	125.4309	0.0000***
Z	0.4565	0.6760	Z	-9.1254	0.0000***
L*	0.4224	0.6627	L*	-11.6316	0.0000***
Pm	-0.7453	0.7720	Pm	17.9051	0.0000***
lagr			Δ lagr		
P	15.7846	0.6076	P	170.0290	0.0000***
Z	0.3501	0.6369	Z	-10.9713	0.0000***
L*	0.3419	0.6330	L*	-15.7866	0.0000***
Pm	-0.3692	0.6440	Pm	25.3382	0.0000***
rer			Δ rer		
P	16.7852	0.5379	P	168.1221	0.0000***
Z	-0.1345	0.4465	Z	-10.7540	0.0000***
L*	-0.1377	0.4455	L*	-15.6056	0.0000***
Pm	-0.2025	0.5802	Pm	25.0204	0.0000***
fdi			Δ fdi		
P	11.3096	0.8808	P	584.1551	0.0000***
Z	0.2522	0.5995	Z	-23.0354	0.0000***
L*	0.2243	0.5883	L*	-54.2450	0.0000***
Pm	-1.1151	0.8676	Pm	94.3592	0.0000***
to			Δ to		
P	10.9307	0.8973	P	134.3111	0.0000***
Z	1.1858	0.8821	Z	-9.2908	0.0000***
L*	1.1892	0.8799	L*	-12.4436	0.0000***
Pm	-1.1782	0.8806	Pm	19.3852	0.0000***

Note: %1 significance level: ***, %5 significance level: **, %10 significance level: *.

Table 4. LM Test Results

Model 1	Test	Test statistics	P value
$lyields = \beta_0 + \beta_1 rer_{it} + \beta_2 fdi_{it} + \beta_3 to_{it} + \beta_4 lagr_{it} + \beta_5 lexp_{it} + \beta_6 lgdp_{it} + \mu_{it}$	LM*	50.46	0.0555

In Table 4, the hypotheses for cross-sectional dependence LM test results were set as follows: H_0 : Residuals are not correlated between units. H_1 : Residuals are correlated between units. These results indicated that according to cross-sectional dependence LM test results in Table 4, the p value was 0.0555 and was greater than 0.05, so the H_0 hypothesis could not be rejected for Model-1. It was concluded that there was no cross-sectional dependence for Model-1 (Yerdelen Tatoğlu, 2024). The second factor to be determined in order to decide on the co-integration test in the

study is to determine whether the model is homogeneous or heterogeneous. For this, homogeneity test must be performed. Since $T > N$, Swamy-S test was preferred to determine homogeneity in the study. If the result of Swamy-S test statistics is greater than the critical values, the parameters are interpreted as heterogeneous and if small, the parameters are interpreted as homogeneous (Baltagi, 2005). Table 5 shows the Swamy-S homogeneity test results.

Table 5. Swamy-s homogeneity test results

Model 1	Chi2 (56)	P-Value
$lyields = \beta_0 + \beta_1 reri_t + \beta_2 fdi_t + \beta_3 to_t + \beta_4 lagrf_{it} + \beta_5 lexp_{it} + \beta_6 lgdp_{it} + \mu_{it}$	2998.35	0.0000**

Note: %1 significance level: ***, %5 significance level: **, %10 significance level: *.

According to the Swamy-S homogeneity test in Table 5, the difference between unit-specific OLS estimators that ignore the panel structure of the data can be tested. If there is no statistically significant difference, the parameters are homogeneous. The hypothesis to be tested for homogeneity is as follows: H_0 : The regression coefficients of all units (or groups) are homogeneous. According to the Swamy-S homogeneity test in Table 5, since the P-value for Model-1 was 0.0000, the H_0 hypothesis was rejected and it was accepted that the parameters were not homogeneous and varied from unit to unit. Slope parameters were heterogeneous according to units (Yerdelen Tatoğlu, 2024). Therefore, it would be appropriate to rely on the results of heterogeneous co-integration tests and use the estimation methods recommended for

heterogeneous panels. Since Model-1 was heterogeneous and there was no cross-sectional dependence, the Pedroni cointegration test suitable for these conditions was chosen. In addition, unlike other cointegration tests, Pedroni allows analysis with more than one independent variable. Since 6 independent variables were used in the study, the Pedroni cointegration test was preferred. Pedroni proposed 7 panel cointegration tests, the main hypothesis of which was H_0 : There is no cointegration relationship for all units of the panel. Of these tests, 4 were panel and 3 were group test statistics. 5 of these tests were parametric and 2 were nonparametric tests. Of the Pedroni tests, 3 were derived for heterogeneous and 4 for homogeneous panels. Table 6 presents the Pedroni cointegration test results

Table 6. Pedroni cointegration test results

Model 1: $lyields = \beta_0 + \beta_1 reri_t + \beta_2 fdi_t + \beta_3 to_t + \beta_4 lagrf_{it} + \beta_5 lexp_{it} + \beta_6 lgdp_{it} + \mu_{it}$		
Test Stats.	Panel	Group
v	.3423	.
rho	-2.16 **	-1.4
T	-9.575 **	-11.17**
adf	-4.823 **	-5.512**
%1=±2.575	%5=±1.960	%10: ±1.645

H_0 : There is no cointegration relationship for all units of the panel. Note: %1 significance level: ***, %5 significance level: **, %10 significance level: *

In Table 6, the lag length in the Pedroni panel cointegration group test results was selected according to AIC. Since all results except the rho value for Model-1 were significant in absolute value at the 95% confidence level (1.960), the H_0 hypothesis was rejected. There is a cointegration relationship. Therefore, the panel cointegration model (long-term relationship) needs to be estimated. In cases where there is no correlation between units in the residuals of the

cointegration model, first generation estimators can be used. Depending on whether the long-term parameter is homogeneous or heterogeneous, the appropriate estimator can be selected. Since it was determined in the study that there was no correlation between units in the models and that the models were heterogeneous, the Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) estimator was preferred as the long-term estimator. Table 7 presents the FMOLS long-run estimation results.

Table 7. FMOLS long run estimation results

	lagr	lgdp	lexp	rer	Fdi	to
Brazil						
beta	1.03	-0.10	0.17	0.00	0.02	-0.01
Se.	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00
t-stat	25.29**	-3.30	4.34**	5.28 **	9.37**	-4.55
Vietnam						
beta	-2.11	0.52	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01
Se.	0.10	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00
t-stat	-20.61	11.67 **	0.35	6.12**	10.51**	16.65**
Colombia						
beta	0.37	0.09	0.20	0.00	0.03	-0.02
Se.	0.14	0.11	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00
t-stat	2.62**	0.85	-2.74	-3.09	5.55**	-6.59
Guatemala						
beta	-0.96	-0.17	0.86	-0.01	-0.00	-0.01
Se.	0.33	0.26	0.22	0.00	0.00	0.00
t-stat	-2.86	-0.63	3.98 **	-4.50	-0.22	-2.80
India						
beta	0.53	-0.94	0.66	-0.00	-0.03	-0.01
Se.	0.09	0.10	0.08	0.00	0.01	0.00
t-stat	5.89**	-9.31	8.32**	-2.40	-4.19	-4.44
Honduras						
beta	0.85	0.08	-0.53	0.01	-0.01	0.01
Se.	0.08	0.07	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00
t-stat	10.86**	1.13	-5.51	9.91**	-3.41	5.15**
Indonesia						
beta	0.86	0.00	-0.28	0.00	0.02	0.01
Se.	0.06	0.07	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00
t-stat	14.12 **	0.01	-4.31	7.35 **	4.68**	6.5**
Mexico						
beta	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Se.	64.36	52.19	23.80	0.18	0.00	1.00
t-stat	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.42	0.00
Uganda						
beta	0.82	-0.68	0.34	0.01	-0.02	0.00
Se.	0.31	0.22	0.21	0.00	0.02	0.01
t-stat	2.66**	-3.07	1.61	4.60**	-0.84	0.11
Panel group						
Beta	0.16	-0.13	0.12	0.00	0.00	-0.00
t-stat	12.66**	-0.88	2.02**	7.76**	7.62**	3.37**
% 1=±2.575 % 5=±1.960 % 10: ±1.645						

Table 7 shows the estimation of the long-term relationship between yields and independent variables for each unit using FMOLS. When the t statistics of the long-term parameter were examined, it was seen that the parameters were significant except for Mexico. In panel group statistics, the t statistics of the long-term parameter were also significant. For the panel group, the variables *lagr*, *lexp*, *rer*, *fdi* and *to* affected the *lyields* variable. 1% increase in agricultural added value increased coffee production by 16%. 1% increase in exports increased coffee production by 12%. Foreign direct investments, the real exchange rate and trade openness, on the other hand, increased coffee production by a very small amount. When the findings were evaluated on

a unit basis, it was seen that agricultural added value increased the production amount in Brazil, Uganda, Indonesia, Colombia, India and Honduras, and the highest increase was in Brazil and Indonesia. The results for Mexico were found to be insignificant. It was concluded that an increase in GDP increased production in Vietnam. A one-unit increase in exports increased production in Brazil, Guatemala and India. It was concluded that the increase real exchange rate increased the amount of production in Brazil, Vietnam, Honduras, Indonesia, Uganda production amount by a very small amount. It was concluded that increase direct foreign investments increased the amount of production in Brazil, Vietnam, Colombia,

Indonesia production amount by a very small amount. It was concluded that increase trade openness increased the amount of production in Vietnam, Honduras, Indonesia production amount by a very small amount. The added value of the agricultural sector does not only mean more production, but is also a fundamental factor in improving the quality of production, increasing productivity, adopting sustainable production methods and being competitive in the global market. Therefore, the added value of the agricultural sector plays a critical role in coffee production. When the results of the study are examined, the increase in the added value of the agricultural sector in Brazil, Uganda, Indonesia, Colombia, India and Honduras is generally associated with the improvement of technologies, production methods and productivity used in agriculture. This can be interpreted as a sign that countries will produce high quality coffee, which will lead to higher prices and greater demand in international markets. The study concluded that economic growth (increasing GDP) is an important factor that increases coffee production for Vietnam. Economic growth leads to increased coffee production, which is linked to greater productivity, investments and consumption demand. It was concluded that there is a positive and limited relationship between the export variable and the amount of coffee production. For Brazil, Guatemala and India, this suggests that exports can promote coffee production through economic growth, income growth, market access and increased production capacity, but the magnitude of the effect is more limited. The positive relationship between real exchange rate and coffee production volume can be associated with economic development and export-oriented growth strategies. Such a relationship shows that real exchange rates have an impact on export revenues, especially in developing countries (Edwards, 1985). When the real exchange rate increases, the value of the local currency decreases, which can make export-oriented products such as coffee more competitive in foreign markets. Increased competitiveness for Brazil, Vietnam, Honduras, Indonesia and Uganda can

encourage coffee producers to produce more (Balan et al., 2018). The increase in foreign direct investments leads to an increase in coffee production. However, the effect of foreign direct investments on coffee production is much lower. Foreign direct investments can contribute to providing resources to local producers, training the workforce, improving infrastructure and even the growth of the local economy. The results obtained in the study indicate that such investments can create a smaller and stable growth in the long term instead of a larger and faster increase for Brazil, Vietnam, Colombia and Indonesia. An increase in trade openness can be expressed as the greater integration of international trade into the economy. In particular, given that agricultural products such as coffee are products subject to foreign trade, it can be expected that as trade openness increases, production and trade with foreign markets will also increase. For Vietnam, Honduras and Indonesia, it can be interpreted that trade openness may encourage coffee producers to produce more, especially in relation to the growth of exports, but since the impact is small, the role of trade openness in increasing coffee production will be limited (Nugroho and Lakner, 2022). If the relationship between the agricultural sector value added and the coffee production amount is positive and significant, it can be interpreted that the increase in coffee production will contribute to the growth of the agricultural sector value added, reinforce the role of the coffee sector in the agricultural economy, and that coffee production continues to create value for the agricultural sector and supports the growth of this sector. Therefore, providing financial incentives to increase the coffee production of these countries, encouraging organic and sustainable agricultural practices to ensure environmental sustainability and developing agricultural insurance systems considering the negative effects of external factors such as climate change can be presented as policy recommendations. The results obtained in the study show that FDI plays an important role in coffee production. Foreign investments can increase production

by contributing to the agricultural sector, particularly through infrastructure, technology, education and market access. Foreign investments can offer modern agricultural techniques, efficient irrigation systems and quality improvements to producers and increase the competitiveness of coffee producing countries in the global coffee market. The effect of increases in exchange rates on coffee production can lead to more competitive prices for coffee exports and allow domestic producers to increase their production in response to rising demand. Therefore, exchange rate stabilization policies can be developed to manage exchange rate fluctuations. Incentives for exporters can be increased. Investments can be made to increase productivity in coffee production. Increasing trade openness (freedom of foreign trade and level of openness to the outside world) can open wider foreign markets to coffee producers, allowing them to increase their production and improve their international competitiveness. Increasing foreign trade can lead to greater demand for both raw coffee exports and processed coffee products in global markets. Therefore, it can be suggested to reduce tariff and customs barriers and strengthen their relations with foreign markets (Nugroho and Lakner, 2022). The findings indicate that the economic structures of coffee-producing countries are open to sectoral diversification, balanced investment policies, and global integration. The absence of the Dutch disease suggests that these countries are allocating external resources not to a single area but to the entire economic structure, thus

supporting long-term growth and preventing economic vulnerabilities. The increase in coffee production with the increase in exports can be interpreted as an important factor in increasing production capacity and efficiency and ensuring that producers earn more income. Therefore, more markets can be opened to coffee producers by increasing export incentives. Incentives such as tax breaks and subsidies can be offered to support exporters. While cointegration and positive relationships do not alone prove the validity of a hypothesis, they are necessary and meaningful steps in testing the consistency of the economic mechanism on which the hypothesis is based within the framework of long-term relationships. Such findings are fundamental indicators that pave the way for structural analyses. Complementary tests such as causality analyses are also recommended to reveal the direction and dynamics of these relationships more clearly (Granger, 1988). Therefore, panel causality analysis was employed to establish the findings of the study on a more solid foundation and to determine the direction of the relationship between the variables. Due to the heterogeneous nature of the model in the panel data set and the lack of cross-sectional dependence, the Granger causality test for heterogeneous panels, developed by Hurlin & Dumitrescu (2012), was used to test the causal relationships between the variables. This method both takes into account the heterogeneity assumption and creates better results in panels with large time dimensions. The results of the causality analysis are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Hurlin and dumitrescu causality test results

Direction of Relationship	W statistics	Z Bar statistics	Prob
lyields→lagr	0.6717	-0.6963	0.4862
lagr→lyields	0.7957	-0.4334	0.6647
lyields→lexp	0.8718	-0.2720	0.7856
lexp→lyields	1.8058	1.7094	0.0474**
lyields→lgdp	2.0143	2.1517	0.0314**
lgdp→lyields	2.7193	3.6472	0.0003*
lyields→rer	4.3612	3.5418	0.0004*
rer→lyields	2.5087	0.7631	0.4454
lyields→fdi	3.0178	4.0357	0.0001*
fdi→lyields	1.2483	0.4965	0.6195
lyields→to	1.0456	0.0967	0.9230
to→lyields	3.4782	-2.1839	0.0290**

Note: %1 significance level: ***, %5 significance level: **, %10 significance level: * .

The findings of the causality analysis presented in Table 8 revealed statistically significant relationships in certain directions between coffee production and selected macroeconomic variables. Within the framework of Dutch Disease, coffee production was found to have a significant impact particularly on the real exchange rate, gross domestic product (GDP), and foreign direct investment. A bidirectional causality was identified between coffee production and GDP, indicating a reciprocal interaction between production and economic growth. Similarly, a bidirectional relationship was observed between exports and coffee production. On the other hand, unidirectional causality from coffee production to the real exchange rate, foreign direct investment, and trade openness was identified. However, no statistically significant causality was found between coffee production and the overall agricultural value added (AGR). These results suggest that coffee production has an impact on certain macroeconomic variables, while exhibiting limited or insignificant relationships with others. The bidirectional causality observed between coffee production and economic growth revealed a mutually reinforcing relationship, rather than the production suppression predicted by the Dutch Disease hypothesis. This indicates that coffee production plays a strategic role in the economy and contributes to the growth process. No significant causality was found between coffee production and agricultural value added (AGR). This is primarily because coffee does not constitute a significant portion of the overall agricultural production. While coffee is an important export product for some countries, the agricultural sector is not solely comprised of coffee. It encompasses various production areas, such as grain, livestock, forestry products, and fishery. Therefore, increases in coffee production may not result in a noticeable change in the total economic value of agriculture. The finding that exports have a unidirectional and significant effect on coffee production indicates that external demand and trade volume guide production decisions. This points to export-driven

production growth rather than the production suppression predicted by the Dutch Disease hypothesis, and is more consistent with resource-led growth dynamics. Bahar & Santos (2018) noted that natural resource exports can steer production rather than suppress it in some economies, describing these effects as resource-led growth. This approach represents a growth model in which natural resources are considered not only as income generators but also as drivers of economic development. In this model, revenues from the resource sector are directed towards areas such as infrastructure investment, human capital development, and industrial diversification, aiming for sustainable growth. Unlike Dutch Disease, resource-led growth envisions that the resource sector can stimulate other sectors instead of suppressing them, creating positive externalities within the economy. In this context, the promotion of coffee production by exports can be considered an indicator of export-driven production growth. Coffee production has a significant impact on the exchange rate. This suggests that an increase in coffee exports can boost foreign currency inflows into the country, leading to an appreciation of the local currency. However, changes in the exchange rate do not have a significant impact on coffee production. In other words, while production affects the exchange rate, the exchange rate does not affect production. This result suggests that production is not harmed by the exchange rate, as in the Dutch Disease theory; on the contrary, coffee production can drive economic indicators. This reveals that the coffee sector plays a significant role not only in agriculture but also in shaping economic policies (Mien and Goujon, 2021). Causality test results indicate that coffee production positively affect foreign direct investment (FDI), but FDI does not affect coffee production. This suggests that the coffee sector is attractive to investors, and increased production attracts investment. Coffee can thus be seen as having strong potential in areas such as sustainability, exports, and local development (Kanyana, 2023). This contradicts the approach

"investing only in the resource sector and damaging other sectors" envisioned by the Dutch Disease. On the contrary, coffee production acts as a sector that receives investment and contributes to economic growth. According to the causality test results, trade openness has a unidirectional and significant effect on coffee production. This suggests that open economic structures play a role in encouraging agricultural production, but coffee production itself does not create a direct impact strong enough to influence trade volume. Most countries leading in coffee exports have diversified their export baskets. Therefore, coffee production may not be a dominant sector sufficient to single-handedly drive the overall trade openness of a country (Nugroho and Lakner, 2022).

4. Conclusion

Coffee, one of the important rituals of many people's lives, is the second most traded product in the world. Oil ranks first, and coffee ranks second. Coffee is one of the most important products affected by climate change. When we consider the ecological balance, diminishing forests and the struggle for sustainability, the question of whether coffee will run out is an important topic. The ecological sustainability of coffee is of great importance for farmers, distributors, cafes and consumers. Four main areas are important for sustainability in coffee production: building healthy soils, improving livelihoods for farmers, increasing biodiversity and ecosystem services, and adapting to climate change. The sustainability of coffee production depends on meeting a certain environmental standard in the process from planting coffee to its production, marketing and distribution, and on the environmental consciousness of enterprises to produce green products and offer them to consumers. In this study, the Dutch disease hypothesis was analyzed for coffee producing countries for the period 1989-2022 using panel data analysis. The existence of a cointegration relationship in the study necessitated the examination of Dutch disease. For this, it was essential to investigate how independent variables affect the dependent variable. When

the long-term coefficients were examined, no Dutch disease findings were found across the panel and on a country basis. In the study, the results of the FMOLS long-term estimator analysis showed that the variables of agricultural value-added, export, real exchange rate, foreign direct investments, and trade openness increase coffee production. The findings suggested that it would be beneficial for the world's top ten coffee-producing countries to promote sustainable agricultural methods, provide attractive tax reductions and incentives for foreign investors, develop exchange rate stabilization policies, reduce tariffs and customs barriers, and implement incentives such as tax cuts and subsidies to support exporters. These are presented as policy recommendations. According to the FMOLS long-term estimation results, the Dutch Disease is not observed in some countries and shows only weak symptoms in others. In Brazil and Indonesia, agricultural production, exports, and exchange rates positively affect coffee production, indicating a strong and competitive sector. Therefore, there are no signs of Dutch Disease in these countries. In Vietnam and Honduras, trade openness and foreign investments also contribute to coffee production, reflecting integration into global markets and the resilience of the sector. Thus, Dutch Disease is not observed in these countries either. The results for Mexico are not significant. There is no clear relationship between coffee production and other economic variables. This may indicate structural problems or data deficiencies in the country but does not alone signify the presence of Dutch Disease. In general, Dutch Disease is not present in most of the analyzed countries. On the contrary, the coffee sector has a structure that can attract investment, is open to international markets, and supports economic growth. These findings are consistent with the literature, which generally associates Dutch Disease with countries that rely on natural resources, have concentrated exports in a single sector, and possess weak institutional infrastructure. It is recommended that agricultural added value be increased, production efficiency and quality be

improved by promoting modern agricultural techniques, and farmer training programs and R&D (research and development) support be strengthened. Additionally, modernizing processing infrastructure, encouraging branding initiatives, and developing strategies to enter new markets are crucial for expanding export capacity in the coffee sector. In order to increase direct foreign investment, it is recommended that special investment incentives be provided for the agricultural sector, bureaucratic obstacles be reduced, and public-private partnerships be supported. This can be presented as a policy recommendation.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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